

KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: extended report on the architecture of the PID registration service

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Abstract (in German)

Die zuverlässige Referenzierung von Forschungsdaten und der ihnen innewohnenden detaillierten Entitäten sind ein Hauptanliegen der FAIR-Prinzipien. In Maßnahme 5.1 verbessern wir den Stand der Technik bei der Zitierung von Forschungsdaten, indem wir eine Infrastruktur zur Referenzierung detaillierter Attribute, hier zunächst Variablen, innerhalb solcher Daten entwickeln. Durch die Zuweisung von PIDs zu diesen Attributen können einzelne Elemente der Datendateien referenziert und mit den erforderlichen Metadaten für den maschinellen und menschlichen Zugriff abgerufen werden. Die PIDs werden nicht nur die Zitierbarkeit in wissenschaftlichen Arbeiten ermöglichen, sondern auch den Zugang zur Verarbeitung der enthaltenen Daten selbst, z.B. in Skriptsprachen wie R oder Python.

Dieser Bericht stellt die erweiterte Architektur für eine allgemeine, wartbare und skalierbare Infrastruktur vor, die die Registrierung von PIDs für kleinräumige Attribute in sozialwissenschaftlichen Forschungsdaten ermöglicht. Neben der Hauptfunktionalität betonen wir wiederverwendbare und verallgemeinerte Komponenten als Blaupause für andere Projekte. Alle entwickelten Komponenten werden als Open-Source-Software veröffentlicht.

Abstract

Reliable referencing research data and their inherent detailed entities are a core requirement of the FAIR principles. In measure 5.1 we enhance the state of the art of citing research data, by developing an infrastructure to reference detailed attributes, here initially variables, within such data. By assigning PIDs to these attributes, individual elements of the data files can be referenced and retrieved with the required metadata for machine-actionable and human access. The PIDs will not only enable citeability within scientific papers but also give access for processing the contained data itself, e.g., within script languages like R or Python.

This report provides the extended envisioned architecture for a general, maintainable, and scalable infrastructure that enables the registration of PIDs for small-scale attributes in Social Science research data. Besides the main functionality, we emphasize reusable and generalized components as a blueprint for other projects. All developed components are published as open-source software.

Keywords:

Persistent Identifiers - PIDs. Research data citation. Research data - Social Sciences. Variables - Social Sciences. Granularity level identification. Research data services - technical infrastructure.

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1. Introduction

The KonsortSWD Measure "TA.5-M.1 Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure" focuses on improving research data citation in the Social Sciences by developing an infrastructure to reference and retrieve dataset elements with associated metadata. This report describes the existing architecture for assigning Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to variables within datasets.

The report outlines the architecture of the PID registration service, which consists of two major components: a server-side REST API and a backend component for verified registration. The central "Registration Service" component can handle any registration process via its main endpoint `/api/register`, focusing on variable registration.

Key functionalities of the service include authentication, metadata extraction and validation, and PID registration. Given its comprehensive functionality, the PID Registrator component uses the ePIC APIⁱ for registration. The architecture is designed to be asynchronous, utilizing a Registration Queue to enhance scalability and enable bulk registration.

The workflow starts with user authentication, followed by variable registration requests containing necessary metadata. The registration process includes metadata extraction, validation, and queuing for PID registration. The final PID is obtained asynchronously.

Technical enhancements include implementing a Registration Queue based on Redisⁱⁱ, chosen for its lightweight, efficient, and scalable nature. The system also has a Web User Interface for monitoring registration jobs and statuses. The API endpoints offer variable verification, registration, and status tracking. The system is documented using Swagger for API descriptions.

This report marks a significant step in the KonsortSWD project, as it is part of Milestone 4: Full-stack implementation of the productive and sustainable infrastructure, providing detailed architecture documentation for the PID registration service. The "KonsortSWD PID Registration Service" software is also available at Zenodo [1], concluding the Milestone 4. The metadata schema is designed to accommodate future enhancements, such as registering questionnaire items and ensuring the system's adaptability and sustainability [2], according to the use case needs [3].

1.1. Organization of this report

This report relates to the technical infrastructure. In Section 2, the general architecture of the PID registration service, the major components are depicted within the registration process, and present a detailed description of the registration stages through workflows.

ⁱ <http://www.pidconsortium.net/>

ⁱⁱ <https://redis.io/>

Concludes within section 3 the architecture and requirements to implement the variable registration service, scheduled according to the milestones planned into phases for September 2022 and September 2023, respectively.

Section 4 points to future service evolution possibilities and the corresponding metadata requirements. It also indicates the essential practices like testing and clean code quality standards and adequate software licenses.¹¹

2. Architecture of the PID registration service

In the following, we describe the general architecture of the PID registration service, and its individual components as shown in the architecture diagram (see Figure 1) in more detail.

2.1. System's architecture

There are two major components within the system architecture. The aim is that any service provider can register an arbitrary number of variables (bulk registration) through one REST API endpoint using a REST client. The first component provides the server-side REST API, whereas the second, backend component, the registration service, handles the correct and verified registration process.

Figure 2: Architecture overview

In the following the architecture and concepts are explained as well as functionalities to the variable registration requirements.

2.2. General description of the architecture and concepts

The diagram shows the "Registration Service", the central component of the architecture. It is designed to be a standalone service that can perform any registration processes via its main endpoint `/api/register`. The endpoint `/variable` is the main endpoint that handles requests for variable registration purposes.

Functionalities belonging together are bundled into components of the service, for example, authentication (*auth*-component), metadata extraction (*MD Extractor* and *MD Validator*), and registration (*PID Registrar*). Since variable registration requires metadata to comply with a pre-defined schema, *MD Extractor* & *Validator* are specific *instances* of a validator and an extractor. Abstractly implementing this enables us to be open for future enhancements, for example, adding other endpoints to register different resource types (Datasets, Studies), and to switch between implementations on a per request basis (prospect).

The same applies to *PID Registrar*. It is a specific registration instance, which uses a particular third-party registration service and its defined endpoints to register PIDs. We chose the Persistent Identifier Consortium for eResearchⁱⁱⁱ (ePIC) API^{iv} for that because it already features all necessary functionality and is well supported. In contrast to the variable-specific *MD Extractor* and *MD Validator* instances, requiring resources respecting a particular schema, the ePIC API is not tight to a specific resource type to obtain a PID.

In general, the architecture of the Registration Service is designed to be asynchronous. For that, we employ a *Registration Queue*, where single variable registration jobs are put. Employing a queue has several advantages:

1. The queue decouples the workload of our registration service from the actual PID registration process of the third-party service (ePIC API). Thus, it makes it asynchronous and more scalable;
2. It enables "bulk registration", which means the registration of many variables at once. The size of the queue (i.e., how many requests can be held by the queue) as well as the number of workers (i.e., parallel registrations) should be a matter of configuration. Although "bulk registration" will not have high priority in the first implementation phase, we designed the architecture like this as prospect. We will initialize the queue with only one worker in the beginning;

ⁱⁱⁱ ePIC is an international consortium provides a reliable Handle-based PID infrastructure for research data. ePIC has currently nine members and it is open for any center that stores scientific/research data. See also: <http://www.pidconsortium.net/>

^{iv} <https://doc.pidconsortium.eu/docs/>

- The queue is designed to be persistent; thus, tasks (i.e., registration requests) that are put on the queue can be restored and will not get lost in case of a service failure.

The actual implementation of the queue is still a matter of choice. Generally, the queue can be implemented as an external service, e.g., with Apache Kafka^v or Redis^{vi} or a part of the registration service itself, while it is implemented via a Spring Boot message queue.

Utilizing a registration queue requires storing the status of a request in an extra database. Along with the status of the variable registration, we store all other metadata of the submitted variable there, for example, the time of registration, the user performing the request, and more. The user may query the status via the `/api/register/variable/status` endpoint.

2.3. Description of the Workflows

In the following, we will describe the workflow, starting from a user, here a data provider or a Research Data Center (RDC), which wants to obtain a persistent identifier (PID) for their variables. We will refer to the steps shown in Figure 2: Workflow diagram, which represents the variable registration service process.

Figure 2: Workflow diagram

^v <https://kafka.apache.org/>

^{vi} <https://redis.io/>

Access to the service is provided via token-based authorization (see *auth*-component in Figure 1: Architecture overview), which the user must obtain first. A valid token can be re-used for a given amount of time. To get a fresh token, the user needs to authenticate via the `/api/register/auth` endpoint beforehand. The general user management will be done via the central GESIS Login^{vii}.

To register a variable, the user needs to send a request to the `/api/register/variable` endpoint (step 1, *Registration Service*). The request contains a JSON file with the required fields for variable registration alongside the authentication token mentioned before. The required metadata fields are listed in PID Service for variables report in the section Metadata Schema for variables [4]. The response returns a status code 200, if the service is available (step 3), and the registration request was successful, 500 and an error message otherwise (step 4). The response has not yet returned the PID registered, since our service is designed to be asynchronous. The final PID can be obtained by requesting the status via the `/api/register/variable/status` endpoint (step 6 and 11).

After receiving the initial request, the component extracts, and transforms (MD Extractor) all data into an internal data structure, based on which a structural and content-based validation (MD Validator) takes place (step 2). Structural validation checks whether all required fields are present (see Section Metadata). Content-based validation checks, for example, whether the provided study DOI exists or whether the fields are in the right format (e.g., publication date). If validation fails, the user receives a negative response code with an error message and the registration is not forwarded (step 3).

After validation, the registration request is placed on to the registration queue (step 4). A worker may pick up the registration request (step 9). Here, the term “worker” is used as a wrapper-term and refers to the component that takes care of the actual PID registration – in section PID Registrar in section 2.1 (see Figure 1). This step finalizes the process of registering a PID.

2.4. Extension of technical implementation

In this section we will describe the extension of the implementation. We extended our implementation to include a registration queue, which is used to queue the registration requests based on Redis, database and API. Below we provide details of the implementation.

2.4.1. Registration Queue

The *Registration Queue* (cf. element “4” in Figure 1 and component “Queue” in Figure 2) is a central component of the PID Registration Service. In this section, we will describe our requirements for the *Registration Queue* and introduce some of the well-known Queue

^{vii} <https://login.gesis.org>

technologies (also known as Message Broker). We will then evaluate these technologies to employ the appropriate one.

2.4.1.1. Design and technical requirements for the Registration Queue

The requirements are divided into two categories: design and technical requirements. Design requirements are architectural requirements related to the worker – also called consumer in the context of the message broker – capabilities and use cases. Technical requirements are mostly associated with deployment and maintenance. The requirements are based on use case needs and the software architecture design.

- a) Design requirements – worker (also known as consumer) capabilities and use cases:
 - Only one worker to process registration data from the queue - initial case.
 - “n” workers for bulk registration (see 2.2) – first production case.
 - “n” workers and n worker groups: specific groups with n worker instances, e.g., to register specific user data or to fulfil fairness of registration (see Queue Integration in 2.4.1.3).
- b) Technical requirements – deployment and maintenance:
 - Installation and performance: lightweight, ease of use, fast and efficient.
 - Scalability: it should decouple the workload as it makes the registration process asynchronous and more scalable.
 - Persistency and Fail-Safety: the queue should be restored, and the messages will not get lost in case of a service failure.
 - Docker support: installation and integration with docker; official docker support.
 - Consumer Capability: one-to-one, one-to-many and groups support.

In the following section we provide an evaluation of message brokers, mainly Redis and Kafka.

2.4.1.2. Evaluation of Message Brokers Redis and Kafka

We evaluated two well-known and state of the art message brokers named Redis and Kafka according to five dimensions: Installation and Performance, Scalability, Persistency and Fail-Safety, Docker Support and Consumer Capability. Table 1 demonstrates the comparison results.

Requirements	Redis	Kafka
Installation and Performance	Lightweight; easy configuration and installation; very fast	Heavyweight; complex configuration; not as fast as Redis
Scalability	Up to millions of messages per second	Up to millions of messages per second
Persistency and Fail-Safety	persistency with configuration; fail-safe	persistency; fail-safe
Docker Support	Official docker support	No official docker support
Consumer Capability	One-to-one and one-to-many; cluster and sentinel support;	One-to-one and one-to-many; cluster and groups support

	groups support with Redis Streaming	
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Table 1: Redis versus Kafka: comparison results according to 5 dimensions.

As shown in Table 1 Kafka can be scaled up to millions of messages per second, supports one-to-many consumers, consumer groups and clustering; it is however heavyweight and has a complex initial configuration.

Redis is lightweight, fast and has easy installation and configuration based on official docker support. It supports one-to-many consumers, consumer groups with Redis Streams, clustering and non-cluster solution for highly availability Redis Sentinel^{viii} as well. In addition, Redis provides features like caching, which could be used in cases e.g., displaying thousands of variables fast and efficiently. We proposed using Redis to implement our Registration Queue.

2.4.1.3. Implementation and Integration of Redis in PID Service

In this section, we will describe the implementation and integration of Redis as *Registration Queue* (cf. element "4" in Figure 1 and component "Queue" in Figure 2 in our PID Service. First, the PID Service needs an appropriate client for implementation and communication with Redis. The client should be fast and efficient to fulfil the Registration Queue requirements. Second, for integration we need to find a Redis data structure that enables a reliable queue implementation.

Java Client: There are many clients available, such as Jedis^{ix}, Lettuce^x and Redisson^{xi}. We chose Jedis, because it is a lightweight client library that is designed for performance and ease of use compared to other Java clients. Therefore, for the sake of convenience and efficiency, initial implementation will be done using Jedis as client.

Queue Integration: Implementation and integration of the Redis as Registration Queue is dependent on the PID Service use cases. Redis data structures and generic implementation of the PID service allows us to choose appropriate data structure as well as Java client.

The initial use case will have only one queue and n-workers/consumers (see Figure 1) working with this queue. To implement the initial use case with only one worker (see 2.4.1.1), we are using Redis data structure *List* based on the first-in-first-out (FIFO) principle. Redis provides additional features that make this pattern more efficient, reliable, and easy to use like *BRPOPLPUSH*^{xii} (Blocking variant of push and pull commands). Blocking means, when the

^{viii} <https://redis.io/docs/management/sentinel/>

^{ix} <https://github.com/redis/jedis>

^x <https://github.com/lettuce-io/lettuce-core>

^{xi} <https://github.com/redisson/redisson>

^{xii} <https://redis.io/commands/brpoplpush/>

source or queue is empty, Redis will block the connection until another client pushes to it or until a timeout.

Another use case points to the fairness of the Registration Queue. Not all users will have the same number of variables. For example, GESIS will have ca. 500.000 variables and SOEP ca. 100.000 variables for registration. When another user with small amounts of variables tries to register, the Registration Queue must ensure the fairness of the registration like a priority queue as well. This can be achieved for example by Redis sorted sets^{xiii} which allow us to specify a score or a priority for the messages added to the queue.

These two use cases are based on n-workers. Another use case, which is based on n-workers and n-worker groups (see requirements in 2.4.1.1) cannot be implemented with the Redis data structures List or Sets mentioned. For this purpose, Redis has another data type, namely Redis Streams^{xiv}. With Redis Streams it is possible to define n-groups for specific tasks.

2.4.2. API Implementation

As proof of concept, we implemented the initial version of the PID Registration Service with minimal requirements, such as variable and status endpoints (cf. element "3" and "5" in Figure 1), authentication and Web User Interface (UI), which we will describe in detail in the next sections (see also section 2.4.3).

"/variable/" Endpoint: This is the starting point of PID Registration Service accepting variable metadata (PID Service for variables report [4]) in JSON format:

- *"/variable/verify"*: for validation of variables.
- *"/variable/register"*: for the registration of variables.

"/variable/status/" Endpoint: This endpoint has the API methods for displaying the job and the variable statuses for a registration request:

- *"/variable/jobs/{username}"* to get job information of an authenticated *user* or
- *"/variable/job/{jobId}"* to get job and its variables information for a given *jobId*

Web UI: The user interface of the PID Registration Service provides appropriate functions to display the job and variable statuses from the variable and status endpoints as well.

Job Information: After successful login, an overview of all running jobs for a user will be shown. Figure 3 shows the jobs information of the user *demo* including its number of jobs and their statuses.

^{xiii} <https://redis.io/docs/data-types/sorted-sets/>

^{xiv} <https://redis.io/docs/data-types/streams/>

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User Job Status

Username	Nr. of Jobs	● Finished	● Pending/Running	● Failed
demo	10	-	1	9

Figure 33: Web User Interface – Jobs overview for signed-in user demo.

By clicking on the number of jobs, the user gets detailed information such as creation date, last update, number of variables, study variables belonging to, and statuses of variables (see Figure 4). The jobs can be filtered by statuses such as Finished, Pending or Running or Failed.

KonsortSWD PID Registration Service [da|ra](#) [Status Page](#) [API Reference](#) [Help](#) [Sign-out\(demo\)](#)

Jobs for User : demo

#	Jobs ID	Creation Date	Last Update	Nr. of Variables	Valid JSON File	Study (DOI) Online	● Finished	● Pending/Running	● Failed
1	03412fed-0d8f-4bce-b6d6-8fc2fe3acc39	2023-11-24 19:07:05.946	2023-11-24 19:07:07.852	5	valid	200	-	-	5
2	771e6dcb-5713-4fc0-a838-9d5da7f355cb	2023-11-20 09:17:50.485	2023-11-20 09:18:03.721	5	valid	200	-	-	5
3	07a9b6f9-b720-40b0-b6e3-f691a8a3bfee	2023-11-19 14:17:58.2	2023-11-19 14:18:27.241	5	valid	200	-	-	5
4	e98ddf94-9494-4fb5-8ee3-d07ba817de25	2023-11-19 14:17:33.351	2023-11-19 14:17:53.187	5	valid	200	-	-	5
5	01e4451e-8f68-4d1a-96ef-c28065f5a6a9	2023-11-19 14:17:27.093	2023-11-19 14:17:42.693	5	valid	200	-	-	5

Figure 4: Jobs for User demo

Detailed information for a specific job can be filtered again by clicking the number of variables or job status. Figure 5 shows the information and statuses of all variables for the job with id "03412fed-0d8f-4bce-b6d6-8fc2fe3acc39". It shows the following information: position of the variable in the JSON file, last update, status of the variable based on validation and registration results, validation status with validations errors and registration errors or the final PID if registration were successful.

KonsortSWD PID Registration Service [da|ra](#) [Status Page](#) [API Reference](#) [Help](#) [Sign-out\(demo\)](#)

Variables for JobID: 03412fed-0d8f-4bce-b6d6-8fc2fe3acc39 ([demo](#))

#	Variables	Last Update	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	Registration Result
1	variable-0	2023-11-24 19:07:07.382	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
2	variable-1	2023-11-24 19:07:07.521	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
3	variable-2	2023-11-24 19:07:07.634	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
4	variable-3	2023-11-24 19:07:07.753	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
5	variable-4	2023-11-24 19:07:07.834	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!

Figure 5: Job Variables

By clicking a variable link in the Job Variables list will give the users the history of variable for the past registrations. Figure 6 shows the history of the variable with VariableID:1.

KonsortSWD PID Registration Service [da|ra](#) [Status Page](#) [API Reference](#) [Help](#) [Sign-out\(demo\)](#)

Variable History for VariableID: 1 (21.T11998/demo.test.1.1680.v1)

#	Position	Job Id	Last Update	Status	Validation Status	Validation Errors	Final PID	Registration Result
1	variable-0	03412fed-0d8f-4bce-b6d6-8fc2fe3acc39	2023-11-24 19:07	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
2	variable-0	771e6dcb-5713-4fc0-a838-9d5da7f355cb	2023-11-20 09:17	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
3	variable-0	07a9b6f9-b720-40b0-b6e3-f691a8a3bfee	2023-11-19 14:18	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
4	variable-0	e98ddf94-9494-4fb5-8ee3-d07ba817de25	2023-11-19 14:17	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!
5	variable-0	01e4451e-8f68-4d1a-96ef-c28065f5a6a9	2023-11-19 14:17	FAILED	valid	-	-	Failed:ServerError!

Figure 6: Variable history information

2.4.3. Swagger API documentation

In this section, we will describe the API Endpoints of the PID Registration Service. The initial implementation has four methods (Figure 7).

Registration		^
POST	/variable/verify This method enables you to verify the variables and the metadata in the JSON file to be registered and returns a validation report.	∨
POST	/variable/register This method enables you to register and verify the variables and the metadata in the JSON file to be registered and returns a jobId to fetch the status of the registration process.	∨ 🔒
GET	/variable/status/jobs/{username} This method returns all running jobs of the user identified by the authorization.	∨ 🔒
GET	/variable/status/job/{jobId} This method returns the status of the verification or register process identified by the jobId.	∨ 🔒

Figure 7: Initial API Methods

Variable verification or validation: This method enables the users to verify the variables and metadata in the JSON to be registered and returns a validation report respectively validation results. Figure 8 shows the validation report for a valid JSON file with no validation errors (constraint violations).

```

Server response
Code    Details
200
Response body
{
  "documentUri": "10.4232/1.1680",
  "constraintViolation": []
}
    
```

Figure 8: Results of variable validation for a valid JSON file.

For an invalid JSON file, Figure 9 shows the validation results with three validation errors including the error message and the variable location of these errors.

```

Server response
Code    Details
200
Response body
{
  "documentUri": "10.4232/1.1680",
  "constraintViolation": [
    {
      "message": "$.variables[1].variableLabel: is missing but it is required",
      "locationInfo": "$.variables[1]"
    },
    {
      "message": "$.variables[3].test: is not defined in the schema and the schema does not allow additional properties",
      "locationInfo": "$.variables[3]"
    },
    {
      "message": "$.variables[3].variableLabel: is missing but it is required",
      "locationInfo": "$.variables[3]"
    }
  ]
}
    
```

Figure 9: Results of variable validation for an invalid JSON file

Variable register: This method enables the users to register and verify the variables and the metadata in the JSON file to be registered and returns a *jobId* to fetch the status of the registration process.

Variable Status - Jobs by username: This method returns all running jobs of the user identified by the authorization. Figure 10 shows the jobs for the user demo.

Figure 10: User Jobs

Variable Statuses - Job by jobId: This method returns the status of the verification or register process identified by the jobId. Figure 11 shows variable statuses for the jobId: *affbff68-71a3-483a-bfcd-47511ba8279d*.

Figure 11: Job Statuses

The demo application for the PID Registration Service is available [5], covering the four methods: verification, registration, identified user jobs and job status. The methods "job" and "jobs status" replace the former "task" and "task status" in the video, but the functionality remains the same.

3. Conclusion

This report completes milestone 4 within measure 5.1: PID Service for variables. In this report we present the extended description of the general architecture., It serves as the main reference for the implementation of the variable registration service. The architecture itself and the metadata schema were in addition modelled in such a way that further entities such as questions from questionnaires could be registered. All services are modelled as generic software components, where applicable. In addition, all software components will be

implemented with testing and clean code quality standards by GESIS and is published under the Apache license. The source code is available as open source at Zenodo [1].

4. Future Work

The service is flexible and allows other data formats, including new attribute levels at the further stages, such as surveys' questions, audio and video data fragments, a selected part of an image, or any digital object elements that register data throughout the various knowledge subject fields. In this sense, further applications of the PID service at other attributes than variables require metadata fields to be foreseen accordingly. Some metadata fields examples that should be envisioned are any digital objects components, inheritance, multilingual and related fields as concept classification and concept classification versions.

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